

PROPERTIES OF A CLAYEY SOIL OF WEST BENGAL. CHEMICAL, ELECTROCHEMICAL, VISCOUS, X-RAY AND PETROGRAPHIC STUDIES

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The chemical, mineralogical, X-ray, electrochemical and viscous studies of the clay fraction of a heavy 'ahtel' soil from Hoogly, W. Bengal are described. On the basis of these studies it is estimated that the clay contains 10, 50 and 40% of montmorillonite, illite and kaolinite respectively. The importance of such studies to various soil types so far as their use, capabilities in agricultural, ceramic and engineering enterprises are concerned has been briefly discussed.

The need of systematic studies on the nature and amounts of secondary silicate minerals, known as clay minerals, present in soils, can no longer be questioned (Joffe, "Pedology", 1949). Such studies afford valuable information which is of vital importance in agricultural, ceramic and engineering enterprises. Chemical, electrochemical, viscous, optical, X-ray and thermal dehydration studies have been requisitioned for this purpose. The present paper records the results obtained with a clayey soil of West Bengal, collected from Hoogly and locally known as 'Ahtel' soil.

EXPERIMENTAL

The 1 micron fraction was isolated from the soil using International-Soda method (Robinson, Imperial Bureau of Soil Science, Technical Bulletin No. 26, 1933). This fraction was repeatedly leached with 0.03N-HCl, excess acid washed off with distilled water, and finally the clay was dispersed in redistilled water.

Chemical Analysis.—The percentages of SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , Fe_2O_3 , MgO , K_2O , CaO of the H-clay, determined by fusion analysis, are 53.80, 30.70, 13.90, 0.51, 2.50 and 0.29 respectively. The presence of 0.20% Ca (0.29% CaO) is rather interesting. Whether the calcium is present within the lattice or is due to the presence of comminuted unweathered primary minerals is still an open question. Assuming that all the potassium comes from illite, the percentage of the latter in the $<1\mu$ 'ahtel' clay comes out to about 40% according to the formula $(\text{OH})_4\text{K}_y(\text{Al}_4\text{Fe}_4\text{Mg}_4\text{Mg}_6)\text{Si}_{10-y}\text{Al}_y\text{O}_{20}$, where y has value of 1.0 (Grim *et al.*, *Amer. Min.*, 1937, 22, 813). Further, if the whole of Mg present in $<1\mu$ H-clay be attributed to its montmorillonite content, the percentage of the latter approximates to about 13% according to the formula $(\text{OH})_2\text{Al}_{1.67}\text{Mg}_{0.33}\text{Si}_4\text{O}_{20}$ (Ross and Hendricks, U. S. Geological Survey Professional Paper No. 205-B, 1945). The percentage of kaolinite in this H-clay, thus, comes to about 46% (100-40-14).

X-ray Studies.—The X-ray patterns were made of the glycerol-solvated, calcium-saturated clay using the Geiger counter X-ray spectrometer (Jeffries and Jackson, *Soil Sci.*, 1949, 68, 57). The complete equipment consists of an X-ray generator, a motor-driven scanning unit and a recorder upon which were reproduced the angles and inten-

sities of the characteristic reflections from the sample. The percentage of minerals in the 'ahtel' clay was estimated by the intensity of the various diffraction lines relative to that of the respective lines of standard patterns. Some of the significant spacings observed in the powder pattern of this clay are $18.4\text{\AA}$, $10.05\text{\AA}$ and $7.25\text{\AA}$, which indicate the presence of montmorillonite, illite and kaolinite in the 'ahtel' clay. The approximate percentages of the three clay minerals as calculated from intensity measurements come to 10, 50, and 40 in the order mentioned above. Considering the limitation of the methods used for measuring intensity arising out of (1) variation of lattice distortion and crystal habit; (2) occurrence of amorphous components in clays and (3) decrease of diffraction intensity with decreasing particle size, the relative amounts of the three clay minerals, as determined by the chemical and X-ray methods, seem to agree fairly well. Factor (2) also renders difficult the interpretation of the analytical data in relation to the amount of different clay minerals present in the clay.

Electrochemical Properties.—The variations in the p_H of 0.91% H-clay on the addition of increasing amounts of NaOH are shown in Figure 1. The p_H -alkali concentration curve shows an initial weak acid character followed by a sharp inflexion at p_H 8.4. The base-exchange capacity calculated at this point in the curve comes to 55.0 milliequivalents per 100 g. of clay. The potentiometric titration curve is apparently similar to that of montmorillonitic clay. This resemblance is, however, only superficial as the presence of three clay minerals is suggested by X-ray data. The presence of appreciable amount of illite in this clay is also indicated by the results of fusion analysis.

FIG 1

Viscous Property.—The viscosity-alkali concentration curve (Fig. 1) of the H-clay, prepared from the 'ahtel' soil, shows the following features: (i) an initial decrease; (ii) then an increase showing a maximum, and (iii) finally a decrease tending to a constant value. The changes in the viscosity in these three stages are, however, very

small. The initial decrease may be ascribed to the presence of illite or kaolinite in this clay (Mukherjee and Mitra, *Nature*, 1944, 154, 821; Chatterjee, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 268) and the subsequent increase to the presence of montmorillonite. The nature of the curve suggests that the amount of montmorillonite present in this clay is very small.

Petrographic Studies.—The amounts of heavy and light minerals present in the fine and coarse sand fractions have been determined to gain, if possible, information on the genesis and development of the 'ahtel' soil. The light and heavy fractions were separated by means of bromoform using a hand centrifuge. These fractions were then examined under a petrographic microscope. The results have been presented in Table I.

TABLE I

	Light fraction (90% by weight).		Heavy fraction (10% by weight).	
Coarse sand	Quartz	... 66%	Iron oxide	... Abundant
	Orthoclase	... 6%	Green horn blende	... Very few
	Microcline	... 9%		
	Plagioclase	... 19%		
	(andesine + labradorite)			
Fine sand	Quartz	... 60%	Iron oxide	... 8%
	Orthoclase	... 6%	(magnetite, and ilmenite)	
	Microcline	... 9%		
	Plagioclase	... 25%		
	(andesine and labradorite)		Iron oxide	... 33%
			(limonite, haematite, etc.)	
			Epidote	... 13%
			Zoisite-clinozoisite	... 21%
			Green horn blende	... 8%
			Brown horn blende	... 2%
			Zircon	... 7%
			Brown tourmaline	... 3%
			Blue tourmaline	... 2%
		Biotite	... 1%	
		Garnet	... 1%	
		Rutile	... 1%	

The results of mineralogical analysis suggest that the 'ahtel' soil is fairly mature, especially as indicated by the high percentages of quartz and zircon present, and that the soil is far away from the parent rock. The soil seems to have been derived from metamorphosed igneous rocks of Chotanagpur region in Bihar.

The practical values of the results detailed in the present paper lies in the fact that they show that 'ahtel' soil has a fair reserve of potassium. The amounts of fertilizer applied should be moderate, for if too little fertilizer is applied to it, the montmorillonite part will adsorb it and will not release the food to the plant (Chatterjee and Marshale *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1950, 54, 671), while with abundance there is a chance of some

of the plant food being lost under moderate to heavy drainage. The relative proportion of the three clay minerals present in 'ahel' soil, as also the nature of the exchangeable cations (Ca, 16.8; Mg, 6.4; K, 2.1 milliequivalents per 100 g. of soil), account for the observed physical and mechanical properties of this soil, which are of importance in engineering enterprises, e.g., swelling, shrinkage, plasticity, permeability and hydration. These indicate that 'ahel' soil is fairly suitable for earth-dam construction and as fill-material after stabilization by densification, but as such not suitable for air-port and high way construction (Chatterjee and Ghosh, *Curr. Sci.*, 1951, 20, 181).

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